

Application Citizen Science Hubs 2024

Section 1 – General information

Name of the main applicant	Prof. Dr. Frank Wesselingh
Applicant organisation	Naturalis Biodiversity Center
E-mail address	frank.wesselingh@naturalis.nl
Telephone number	06 23636030
Postal address	P.O. Box 9517, 2300 RA Leiden
ORCID ID (if applicable)	0000-0003-3655-0701

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Roeland Bom
Applicant organisation	NIOZ - Nederlands instituut voor Onderzoek ter Zee
E-mail address	roeland.bom@nioz.nl
Telephone number	0222 369 300
Postal address	PO Box 59, 1790 AB Den Burg (Texel)
ORCID ID (if applicable)	0000-0001-8180-1958

Lay summary in English (50-100 words)

Title of the proposal	<i>CS@Sea, the citizen science hub for marine and coastal natural history searchers and researchers</i>
Author, Affiliation	<i>Frank Wesselingh, Naturalis & Roeland Bom, NIOZ</i>
Text	<i>A long tradition of Citizen Science (CS) exists in the Dutch natural history domain. However, CS- initiatives are dispersed and not well embedded in institutes. In this project we will build CS@Sea - a hub supporting the work of citizen scientists on marine and coastal nature. Six different flagship CS projects, all with their own citizen scientists and needs, together with a wider stakeholder assessment, will shape the organisation and services of the hub. This will lead to an institutionally-embedded CS-Hub optimally designed to serve all future CS-initiatives in the NL in the domains of biodiversity and natural history.</i>

Lekensamenvatting (Lay summary in Dutch) (50-100 woorden)

Titel van de aanvraag	<i>CS@Sea, de Citizen Science hub voor zoekers en onderzoekers van zee en kust</i>
Author, Instelling	<i>Frank Wesselingh, Naturalis & Roeland Bom, NIOZ</i>
Nederlandse tekst	<i>Burgerwetenschap ofwel Citizen Science (CS) speelt een essentiële rol in natuurhistorisch/ biodiversiteitsonderzoek in Nederland. Burgerwetenschappers doen zelf onderzoek en/of spelen rollen in onderzoeksprogramma's. CS-initiatieven zijn versnipperd en er is behoefte aan een centraal loket waar expertise en steun voor dit soort projecten is gebundeld. De nieuwe CS@Sea hub zal kennis en steun bundelen voor onderzoekers van kust en zee. Daarmee wordt CS ingebed in onze instituten. Aan de hand van de behoeften en expertise van burgerwetenschappers en van zes CS-projecten bouwen we een hub die optimaal is ingericht om toekomstige CS-initiatieven op het gebied van natuur te ondersteunen</i>

Section 2 – Description of the Citizen Science Hub

1. Team composition: quality of the team (criterion 1: 30%)

The CS@Sea team represents a strong network of leading organisations that house important Citizen Science (CS) projects active in the Dutch seas and coast with a long track record in CS - Naturalis Biodiversity Center is the Dutch Natural History museum and biodiversity research institute, The Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ) is the leading national marine research institute, Stichting ANEMOON (Anemooon Foundation) has an extensive track record in marine and coastal monitoring with Citizen Scientists (CSs) and our external partner the Leiden University Citizen Science Lab is a leading research hub in the academic domain. CS@Sea partners further bring a large network of societal and institutional partners active in marine and coastal environments. We run programs that support both individuals and groups of citizen scientists, helping them to investigate and publish valuable information on living and fossil species. Several of our programs systematically involve CSs in sampling and observations, such as the Beach Monitoring Program from Stichting ANEMOON and the SIBES project from the NIOZ. Furthermore, we are active in the coordination of outreach events with CSs such as the National Shell Counting Day ('Schelpenteldag') that benefits from our extensive communication and outreach expertise and the free accessible podia in our institutes such as the LiveScience Venue at Naturalis.

TABLE 1 - CS@Sea team	Expertise & Experience	Role in CS@Sea
Frank Wesselingh (Naturalis)	Coordination CS projects, CS outreach and data	Hub Coordinator, flagship project lead
Roeland Bom (NIOZ)	Coordination CS involvement NIOZ	Hub co-coordinator, flagship project lead
Adriaan Gmelig Meyling (Anemooon)	Coordination CS monitoring; data and outreach	Coordinator two flagship projects
Leonie Bakker (Naturalis)	Education & stakeholder engagement project lead	Stakeholder and education expertise
Bart Braun (Naturalis)	Science Communication and engagement	Communication and engagement expertise
Allert Bijleveld (NIOZ)	Coordination CS involvement NIOZ	Flagship project lead
Elaine van Ommen Kloeke (Naturalis)	Coordination CS in ARISE programme	Flagship project lead

Each of the team members is currently involved in CS projects and brings a strong track record of experience concerning CS involvement covering the entire participation ladder (from observers to leading professional level CSs); **we jointly perform many tasks that are critical to a successful hub (hands-on experience, facilities, outreach, communication, education, data (management), community management, writing and supporting papers written by CS, advice)**. Frank Wesselingh (Naturalis) leads the NWO-funded LegaSea project that investigates the combined use of CS (for data gathering and validation) and artificial intelligence, coordinates the CS-strandfossielen project with a dedicated CS community, has a long publication track record with CSs and initiated the annual Dutch shell counting day. Roeland Bom (NIOZ) coordinates and manages the involvement of CSs in the NIOZ shorebirds program in which observers are supported to report occurrences of marked birds. Adriaan Gmelig Meyling (Stichting ANEMOON) is chairman of a national organisation that coordinates several marine CS monitoring programs. Some already run for decades; viz. beach monitoring (SMP project) and monitoring of the subtidal zone with divers (the MOO project). In both cases hundreds of volunteers are involved. The monitoring data are used to provide advice to government stakeholders, and for e.g. protection of species and habitats. He is active in science communication and outreach. Leonie Bakker (Naturalis) coordinates educational programs and outreach events focussed on a wide audience involving a broad network of stakeholders. Bart Braun (Naturalis) is an authority on science communication, public engagement, runs communication courses and is active in community management through his involvement in several Dutch public biodiversity days. Allert Bijleveld (NIOZ) coordinates SIBES, the annual sampling of intertidal macrofauna across the Dutch Wadden Sea ecosystem, that heavily relies on CS participation. Elaine Kloeke van Ommen (Naturalis) coordinates the extensive ARISE program that involves the participation of CS for species discovery and validation. **But the team is broader and involves in total 20 staff of the partner institutes** (see in-kind matching). The involved staff will regularly meet, exchange experiences and expertise and identify needs thereby building a shared ownership and very strong and broad expertise base for the hub.

Our institutional network and underlying CS-programs bring a broad range of expertise relevant to the CS hub. With our communication and outreach expertise we build and maintain relationships and ongoing involvement of CSs. Our extensive education expertise can effectively shape CS training and outreach programs. Our biodiversity data collection and processing expertise is important for CS projects to contribute to global open access datasets for research. Furthermore, we host expertise domains relevant to CSs such as legal expertise (sampling permits etc.), scientific methodology, fair data management, advanced analytics, data publication and lab facilities. External partnerships such as the Leiden Biodiversity Network (LBN), which includes the City of Leiden, the University of Applied Sciences, Leiden University, and the Citizen Science Lab, bring complementary expertise to the CS@Sea Hub via joint projects, and mutual learning and knowledge exchange activities. However, we face a number of **challenges**. We **lack the organisation/coordination capacity** to investigate, guide, disseminate and embed CS within, and coordinate between our institutes. Furthermore, **we lack the capacity for embedding our CS-activities in a wider engagement strategy**. Finally, **our online tools are not well integrated** and thereby not an optimally effective for CS projects.

2. Project plan (criterion 2: 40%)

The **CS@Sea hub** will provide **coordination**, expertise, support for staff, CS projects and CSs. The hub will organize public engagement/outreach events, contains physical places (podia) to meet, engage and host training events. It will erect an online platform that integrates (access to) apps and programs for species recognition, data collection, information sources, community management and educational modules and will connect our CS work to educational programs. **The aim of CS@Sea is to organise and coordinate our institutional CS-activities in order to empower and support existing, and raise the new generation of, citizen scientists.**

Tasks of the hub are: (A) to connect and engage individuals and groups of CS with researchers and institutes, but also with the wider public through a public service point, engagement program and events, (B) to support individuals, and groups of, CSs to find information, connections and facilities they are seeking for their projects, (C) to organise stakeholder engagement events and assessments to identify needs and embed these into the hub design and activities, (D) coordinate the development of digital CS solutions across institutes, (E) host/support training courses for CSs and researchers, (F) to provide training opportunities for students and researchers in communication and outreach and (G) to initiate new CS programs and support project applications. And finally (H) by regularly convening the staff members involved in the hub to share experiences and best practices, the hub will drive professionalization and increase visibility of those involved with CS activities in our institutes.

From the start CS@Sea will also function as **the public service point** for CSs questions and requests. CS@Sea will deliver the following **services and benefits** to both CSs, staff and institutes working with CS: (1) access to scientific infrastructure (labs, libraries, collections) and expertise (methodological, legal and communication expertise); (2) a focal point for CSs enquiries (“vraagbaak”); (3) a digital platform (website) for hosting training programs, (4) embed a repository for publications by CS societies (natuurtijdschriften.nl) and (5) online data portals for identification apps o.a. Soortzoekers and Obsidentify as well as (6) sample and collection registration modules.

TABLE 2 - Flagship Programs	Characterization & Aim	Challenges to be addressed in hub
Beach fossils - Frank Wesselingh (Naturalis)	Inventory of the fossil shells from the coast	CSs management and data collection
Waders - Roeland Bom (NIOZ)	Tracking bottlenecks for shorebirds success	CSs participation, education and outreach
Green Beach - Julia van Beinum (Anemoon)	Continuous monitoring of life in the shorezone	CSs coordination and outreach
Intertidal Life - Brendan Oonk (Anemoon)	Beach trawling & intertidal hard substrate monitoring	CSs coordination and innovation
SIBES - Allert Bijleveld (NIOZ)	Annual monitoring of benthic life in tidal ecosystems	CSs communication and management
ARISE - Elaine van Ommen Kloeke (Naturalis)	Authoritative and Rapid Identification System for Essential biodiversity information	CS sampling, communication and engagement

Collaborations & agreements with partners to provide services to users of the hub – **Partner institute staff involved in CS, six flagship projects and two stakeholder assessments will shape the exact program and priorities of the hub.** The expertise housed within the projects and by **staff** involved will benefit the hub. Within the hub we will bring together all staff on a regular base to exchange best practices and challenges within their respective projects and dealings with CSs creating the joint expertise base for the hub. We will coordinate the development and inclusion of relevant digital initiatives and products from our institutes into the hub. Each of the six **flagship** projects has different challenges that will be addressed (Table 2). These include lab analytical support for **individual** CSs, continued CSs participation and support and effective feedback mechanisms for research programs to ensure continued recognition for involved citizens, but also basic education modules for CSs. With each project a collaboration agreement will be made for the arrangements of services, expertise and support (incl. costs) to and from the Hub. Through our network, and supported by a communication plan, we invite CSs working on nature of sea and coast to engage with our hub. CSs questions will be managed by the hub manager who will respond or link to experts or labs, at first within the consortium and guard follow-up. The hub will have a budget to support such requests. Naturalis will provide a podium in Live Science, the free accessible venue that is our main public interface between science and public. Furthermore, Naturalis will bring infrastructure and expertise for online hosting and data handling, communication, legal and educational expertise. NIOZ will provide marine ecosystem expertise and infrastructure and CSs sampling kits and shipping time. Stichting ANEMOON will provide marine biotic expertise and societal stakeholder engagement modules. The CS@Sea Hub will be available for external partners, such as researchers at Leiden University’s Citizen Science Lab, to study the impact of a diverse range of projects and co-develop guidance for the wider field of practice, which will also benefit the hub program and design. We will seek additional regional education centre partners to participate in the hub.

Current situation at the research organisations - All participating organizations are strongly involved in a wide variety of CS projects that cover the entire engagement ladder and stakeholder spectrum and that bring a wide network of societal partners. Naturalis currently houses at about ten CS initiatives, some of them part of larger programs such ARISE and eDentity, and hosts/supports over 50 CS (guest) researchers. It has the desire to increase impact by coordinating engagement and to link citizen research to a broader audience. The NIOZ relies on the contribution of volunteers and CSs in two extensive monitoring and research initiatives. The successful long-

standing coastal monitoring programs of Stichting ANEMOON entirely rely on hundreds of volunteers and involve a wide array of CS. The partners already collaborate in CS initiatives such as the shell counting day (ANEMOON, Naturalis) and building a species reference database for all known multicellular species in the Netherlands with aid of CSs and automated species monitoring (ARISE: Naturalis, ANEMOON). With external partners we collaborate on initiatives such as ‘Expeditie Stadsnatuur Leiden’ (LBN, CS Lab). **CS@Sea will extend and strengthen existing institutional and personal collaborations** and benefit from our joint projects and overlapping expertise in marine and coastal ecosystems. The hub will identify and engage with further partners throughout the project duration. **The CS hub will be paramount for institutional support and embedding of Citizen Science** and recognition of researchers involved in CS (see below).

	2025Q3	2025Q4	2026-1	2026-2	2027-1	2027-2	2028-1	2028-2	2029-1
Start CS@Sea, Hiring Project Manager	M1								
Kickoff (M2); Stakeholder engagement meeting I (M3)		M2/M3							
Workplan		M4							
Building the Hub: desk & online infrastructure: opening			M5						
Public Service point									
Annual Progress assessments									
Stakeholder engagement meeting II				M6					
Mid term review and Continuity Plan CS@Nature					M7				
Working towards CS@Nature									M8

Expected intervention measures to extend the tasks and services - The hiring of a hub coordinator (Table 3, milestone **M1**) will start the process to organize and shape the hub. During the kick-off meeting that will include all participating staff of the partner institutes, the needs and contributions of the partner organisations, involved staff and projects will be assessed and we will formulate a joint framework of shared values and approaches (**M2**). This will create ownership and help us to guide the activities of the hub. We also will start the process of coordinating all digital infrastructural initiatives between Naturalis, NIOZ and ANEMOON in order to maximise synergy with existing web portals, data infrastructure and apps. A stakeholder engagement meeting with representatives of CSs will explore their needs relevant for the hub design and program (**M3**). This will lead to a detailed plan for building the hub and its program, including a Dutch name (**M4**), and a timeline that includes progress evaluation (see below) and an initial strategy to identify additional funding opportunities. Furthermore we will approach regional outreach centres that can act as nature hotspots: meeting places for public and experts that organise CS events as part of the CS@Sea program following archeohotspots (www.archeohotspots.nl) where experts and public meet. Within the plan also the role of regional partners and further engagement of societies will be detailed. Once the physical hub and website are in place, an official opening of the hub will be organized to attract publicity and celebrate the start (**M5**). The hub will organise annual CS outreach and training days, regional thematic meetings, public events, educational programs and activities, publicity events and celebrations. Finally, a second stakeholder workshop (**M6**) will inform the Mid Term Review and will be used to establish a plan for the second half of the project (**M7**). Thereafter the hub will initiate new CS program proposals that can support a business case for an extended and expanded CS@Nature hub (**M8**). Throughout, we will identify and invite additional external partners and networks to strengthen the hub.

Governance - The hub will be governed by the **Supervisory Board (SB) that is the ultimate decision-making body** consisting of partner representatives. The SB meets twice a year to discuss progress and reinforce collaboration between partners and with stakeholders. An extensive advisory board consisting of stakeholder and expert representatives will ensure continued engagement of the hub with societal partners.

Organisation and sustainable institutional embedding of the hub: from CS@Sea to CS@Nature. The Hub coordinator is hosted by Naturalis as part of our Engagement Office and will be present at NIOZ and engage with ANEMOON monthly, and meet with external partners such as those in LBN quarterly. All participating staff that will shape the hub will convene regularly to discuss progress, identify needs and build a joint expertise base for the hub. **During years 1 & 2 the focus is on building a functioning and flourishing hub** covering sea and shore that is found, used and valued by citizen scientists and stakeholders. **During years 3 & 4 the focus will shift to develop and support new CS programs and expand into a wider CS@Nature hub.** The hub must grow and attract further partners and project funding to continue beyond the project duration and beyond coastal ecosystems. We expect researchers in partner organisations, and invite others, to engage the hub in new project proposals, initiatives and events involving CS. **At the end of the project a plan and business case for the continuation of the hub must be agreed** by the partners (Milestone **M8**).

3. Existing network and network expansion (criterion 3: 20%)

CS@Sea consolidates existing institutional and programme collaborations and shapes new collaborations resulting in a strong community in which societal stakeholders involved in investigating and monitoring the nature of the Dutch coastal regions participate.

Integration of CS@Sea in existing networks - CS@Sea will integrate the current dispersed network of the partner organisations and their projects into a single hub that will actively engage into new projects and partnerships in nature-based themes around sea and coast. Examples of **successful existing collaborations** are the ARISE program (Authoritative and Rapid Identification of Species and Ecosystems where Naturalis, ANEMOON & NIOZ participate), the 'Expeditie Stadsnatuur Leiden' initiative of the Leiden Biodiversity Network (including Naturalis and the CS-Lab UL) and the strandschelpenteldag (beach shells counting day: a collaboration of Naturalis & ANEMOON with a range of other partners).

Societal partners of CS@Sea - The strong involvement of Stichting ANEMOON, a successful grassroots organisation of citizen coastal research and monitoring, ensures that our hub is well connected to a wide variety of citizen scientists active with the study and conservation of marine and coastal biodiversity. The hub will help ANEMOON to initiate new intertidal monitoring research projects. The six flagship projects indirectly link us to a wide array of stakeholders covering the entire knowledge chain and societal breadth. This includes societies such as the Dutch Malacological Society and SOVON, regional education centres in the coastal zone (e.g. Terra Maris, NMR, Ecomare), NGOs (e.g. Stichting de Noordzee, IVN), governmental stakeholders such as ministries and agencies and industrial partners such as the offshore wind farming industries. In 2025 a new major offshore marine monitoring program, Noordzeker (Naturalis, NIOZ) with CS components, will start that further offers opportunities to embolden project involvement in CS@Sea. Throughout the duration of the program we will actively seek collaborations with societal partners.

Communication as key to an expanding hub for nature – At the start of the program we will first establish together our key values and messages that we want to publicly convey through the CS-Hub. In the first two years all communication efforts will be directed to connect all relevant stakeholders and especially CSs of the CS@Sea hub. The hub coordinator will coordinate communication with support of the communication experts of the partners. For this we will use our existing networks, the networks of the flagship projects and the extensive network of the annual Shell Counting Day to connect to existing and potential new CSs. All people involved agreed to serve as active ambassadors for CS@Sea. We will use a diversity of media channels (e.g., Nature Today, diverse social media outlets including our institutional outlets) and our extensive media contacts. We will be present at events of relevance for nature of sea and coast such as conventions (e.g. Duikvaker Beurs) and meetings of CS societies (such as the Dutch Malacological Society). The first stakeholder assessment (**M2**) will specifically investigate the needs of our CSs in respect to information and communication and shape the final communication plan and actions. Halfway the program, we will organise a second stakeholder meeting that will include an exploration for the communication strategy for the intended expansion of the hub into a CS@Nature hub (**M8**). Finally, CS@Sea will organise an event where we share good practices in effective communication with, and for CSs.

The future of CS@Sea - The hub focuses on biodiversity, ecosystem and natural history themes of sea and coast. By initially restricting ourselves to sea and coast we achieve that (a) the often overlooked marine biodiversity becomes more visible to a wider audience and (b) we can start building a CS-hub in a focussed manor, optimally exploiting the synergy between the partners and keeping the project feasible to manage. CS@Sea has a good starting position with collaborations, flagships projects and an important expertise base in place. The diverse needs of the six projects and the connected citizen scientists ensures that the developed CS portal accommodates for a wide variety of projects and needs. With the midterm transition towards a broader CS@Nature we will build a hub that will widen engagement and attract funding to build a business case to allow the hub to continue flourishing after the project plan.

4. Impact (criterion 4: 10%)

CS@Sea will generate **measurable and visible impact within and between our organisations, for CSs, the CS community, scientific impact and societal impact.**

Institutional impact - The CS@Sea hub will **ensure organisational embedding** of our CS-activities and **strengthen institutional collaboration**. By involving CS-activities of our researchers, educators, collection managers and communicators as part of the hub we make our work visible to management and enable them to assess our CS activities under the “recognition and award” system. The hub will result in a close community of staff in the different institutes working with CSs bringing a wide range of expertise. The hub will be the place to share best practices and learn from failures among colleagues and with citizen scientists. This will help to professionalize and optimize CS engagement into our organisations and embedding in strategic planning goals. All combined we will become more effective, active and successful in initiating and organizing impactful CS-projects with full institutional support which helps to meet our societal and scientific ambitions concerning nature and biodiversity. Furthermore, the integration of the engagement ladder philosophy within our hub will broaden the public appeal and support base for CS activities in general and public interest and action in the field of (coastal) nature in particular.

CS community impact - The Netherlands has a very diverse and active citizen science community working within the field of nature of sea and shore. Individual CSs often face difficulties to access professional lab facilities and expertise they need for their projects and may not always feel valued for their efforts. Several organizations, such as ANEMOON, are all about citizen engagement. They provide essential knowledge and capacity to conduct monitoring (for e.g. policy), investigate and understand these ecosystems and generate important publicity. These organisations are hugely impactful, but are vulnerable in terms of staffing and continued funding and participation within the hub may help to strengthen their continuity. **CS@Sea will improve support for individual CSs and provide better institutional collaboration for CS organisations** such as ANEMOON **strengthening their continued activities**. Finally, there is a general need to keep recruiting and educating the CSs of the future through an interested-participating-partner spectrum. The envisaged outreach and engagement activities that result from the unique and strong combination of research and museum will strengthen this spectrum that we need to **support, recruit and train the CSs of the future**. This also will lead to **higher appreciation** for the roles our CSs play.

Scientific impact - Our marine and coastal regions face increasingly severe impact of climate change and human activities (e.g. disturbances, invasive species, mass mortality events). The projected warming and sea level rise affects entire ecosystems and the services they provide. The coordinated effort to monitor, understand and deal with these changes is paramount. For this we need deep and continued collaboration between professional and non-professional actors that keeps improving techniques and data standards required for effective monitoring and action. CS@Sea will **improve scientific consistency** of all involved projects and raise methodological levels of involved CSs through training and therefore **improve our understanding of the ecosystem dynamics, vulnerabilities and development of effective measures for marine and coastal nature to adapt**.

Societal impact - CS@Sea will embolden the institutional and citizen networks and collaborations that are required to shape and monitor the wellbeing of Dutch nature in times of rapid change and threats. The flagship projects and the hub itself will be hugely beneficial to green policy targets ranging from coastal municipalities aiming for green quality marks in the Green Beach project to monitoring for national and EU based policy schemes. The embedding of CS in our institutes will support sustainable and durable involvement of CSs in our society. Together we can shape public opinion effectively and thereby set conservation and monitoring agendas for the sea and coast at first, and eventually the entire Dutch nature. Our coastal nature realizes billions worth of economic value through food, tourism and other activities: ensuring the continued health of the ecosystem is a major societal task in which CSs are paramount.

Monitoring - The monitoring of our success will be a **process** with planned moments, such as the annual Supervisory Board review and The Mid Term Review that includes the outcomes of the second stakeholder meeting. During the kick-off phase we will formulate SMART targets to assess our impact. Intended measurable targets for **institutional impact** include: numerical participation of staff involved, to show the integration of CS-targets into the next generation of institutional strategic plans and the continuation of the hub beyond the project period. **CS community impact** will be measured by new integrated monitoring programs covering the entire coastal zone, increased numbers of CSs engaging with projects and by increased satisfaction among a key-user group to be polled at the start and the end of the project period. **Scientific impact monitoring** will consist of tracking publications, data volume monitoring and the successful initiation and funding of new research projects of CSs or with CSs. **Societal impact** will be measured by the number of participants in education schemes, outreach events and the number of publications (articles in mainstream and interested media, social media use).

Total request from NWO

Type of costs	Short description	Costs in euros
Personnel to be hired –	Hub coordinator 0,20 FTE total	31.707,00 €
Personnel to be hired –	Citizen Science lead/hub manager 1,55 FTE total	176.421,00 €
Personnel to be hired –	Communication advisor 0,40 FTE total	45.528,00 €
Personnel to be hired –	CS app and database developer 0,35 FTE total	40.785,50 €
Personnel to be hired –	Data manager shorebirds 0,15 FTE total	15.040,50 €
Personnel to be hired –	Data manager SIBES 0,05 FTE total	5.826,50 €
Personnel to be hired –	Data coordination 0,05 FTE total	4.403,75 €
Organising workshops and symposia	Launching conference	1.000,00 €
Organising workshops and symposia	venue costs 16 meetings with CSs/stakeholders	8.000,00 €
Purchase of services (sub-contractors)	ANEMOON coordination #1 Green Beach	20.000,00 €
Purchase of services (sub-contractors)	ANEMOON coordination #2 Intertidal	18.000,00 €
Other	Analytical budget for individual CS requests	4.000,00€
Purchase of services (sub-contractors)	Building website	4.000,00€
Travel and accommodation costs project participants	Travel between Leiden, Texel and venues for project team members	2.900,00 €
Purchase of services (sub-contractors)	Education module building	4.000,00€
Purchase of services (sub-contractors)	Database optimization	18.000,00€
Total request from NWO		399.612,25€

Section 4 – Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
 - The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
 - I have completed this application form truthfully.
-